

Epiploic Appendagitis of the Transverse Colon: A Rare Localization of a Benign and Frequently Misdiagnosed Condition

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Abstract

Appendagitis, a rare cause of acute abdominal pain, is an isolated inflammation of the omental appendix that often goes unrecognized. It is mainly diagnosed radiologically, thereby avoiding unnecessary surgery. We reported the case of a diabetic patient with appendagitis of the transverse colon, an exceptional location, which responded favorably to medical treatment.

Introduction

Epiploic appendicitis is a rare and often overlooked cause of acute abdominal pain. It corresponds to isolated inflammation of an epiploic appendix, usually secondary to torsion or thrombosis of its drainage vein. Although benign, this condition can mimic a surgical presentation.

Diagnosis is based primarily on imaging, particularly abdominal computed tomography, which allows characteristic signs to be recognized and inappropriate surgical management to be avoided.

Case Presentation

Ms. F.H., aged 53, with type 2 diabetes and taking oral antidiabetic medication, presented to the emergency department with constant stabbing pain in the right hypochondrium without any other associated digestive symptoms, in the absence of fever and with no change in her general condition. Clinical examination revealed significant tenderness in the right upper quadrant without guarding or contracture. Laboratory tests showed signs of inflammation with a CRP level of 166 mg/L and hyperleukocytosis at 12000/mm³. An abdominal-pelvic CT scan with contrast injection was requested, revealing significant densification of the

omental fat adjacent to the transverse colon, with hyperdense linear streaks adjacent to the right anterolateral abdominal wall, confirming the diagnosis of omental appendicitis of the transverse colon.

Discussion

Epiploic appendicitis is a rare and benign cause of acute abdominal pain, occurring mainly in adults between the ages of 20 and 50 [1], often confused with other urgent surgical conditions, such as acute appendicitis or diverticulitis. It corresponds to ischemic inflammation of an omental appendage, which are small peritoneal fat fringes attached along the colon, from the cecum to the rectosigmoid junction.

Each individual has around a hundred of these appendages, measuring between 0.5 and 5 cm. Their fragile vascularization and pedunculated shape promote torsion or venous thrombosis, the main pathophysiological mechanisms responsible for inflammation and fatty necrosis [2,3]. Obesity is a recognized risk factor due to the increased number and volume of omental appendages in these patients [4]. In our case, the patient had a body mass index of 30 kg/m², which classified her as moderately obese.

More Information

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The majority of appendicitis cases occur in the sigmoid colon (approximately 57%) and the cecum (26%), while cases in the transverse colon remain rare ($\approx 6\%$) [5]. In our observation, the transverse topography makes this case particularly interesting, due to the rarity of this location and the similarity of the symptoms to other upper abdominal conditions (e.g., colitis or pancreatitis).

Abdominal CT remains the gold standard examination, enabling a positive diagnosis and avoiding unnecessary surgical intervention. The typical appearance is that of an oval formation, with fatty density (-50 to -100 HU), well defined, in close contact with the colonic wall, surrounded by a peripheral hyperdense rim (“ring

sign”) corresponding to the inflammatory reaction of the serosa [6]. Sometimes, a small hyperdense center may indicate vascular thrombosis. These signs were found in our patient, confirming the diagnosis of epiploic appendicitis in the transverse colon.

Treatment is primarily conservative, based on analgesics and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, with a favorable outcome within a few days to a week [7]. Antibiotics are not routinely indicated, and surgery is only indicated in cases of complications (persistent torsion, abscess, or peritonitis). In our case, the patient received purely symptomatic treatment with complete resolution of pain in less than a week, confirming the benign and self-resolving nature of this condition.

Figure 1. Abdominal Imaging of Epiploic Appendicitis of the Transverse Colon

Conclusions

Although omental appendicitis is a rare and benign condition, it should be considered in cases of localized abdominal pain, especially when laboratory tests are normal. Computed tomography plays an essential role in confirming the diagnosis and helps to avoid unnecessary investigations or procedures. Recognition of this condition is therefore essential, particularly for atypical locations such as the transverse colon, in order to optimize management and reassure the patient that the condition will resolve spontaneously.

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